

INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF USE OF RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES IN UZBEKISTAN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. *Uzbekistan, with its significant potential for renewable energy resources such as solar, wind, and hydropower, faces the dual challenge of meeting growing energy demands while reducing environmental impact. This paper explores strategies for increasing the efficiency of renewable energy utilization within the country's industrial enterprises. Key aspects include the integration of modern technologies, optimization of energy management systems, and implementation of energy-efficient practices tailored to the industrial sector. The study also highlights policy measures, incentives, and technical solutions that support the adoption of renewable energy. Case studies of successful implementations in Uzbekistan are analyzed, demonstrating the economic and environmental benefits of these initiatives. The findings underline the critical role of innovation and government support in fostering sustainable energy solutions, contributing to Uzbekistan's energy security and global commitments to carbon neutrality.*

Keywords: *energy, sustainable energy solutions, energy demands, reducing environmental, industrial enterprises.*

1.Introduction

Since the first years of independence, the main goal of Uzbekistan's energy policy has been to provide stable energy resources to all sectors of the economy and the population. However, the aggravation of the geopolitical situation observed in the world in recent years and the economic restrictions related to the Covid-19 pandemic put the task of improving the scientific and methodological foundations for the development of this system. According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" dated January 28, 2022 No. taking measures to reduce the volume of harmful gases by 20%", "2026 By 2018, in exchange for increasing the share of renewable energy sources to 25%, saving nearly 3 billion cubic meters of natural gas per year" and "reducing losses in industrial sectors and increasing the efficiency of resource use" have been set. It is necessary to further expand the scientific-methodological base for the use of regenerative energy systems in the implementation of these tasks. [1]

Renewable alternative energy sources are very important in saving natural energy resources and using them efficiently. In Uzbekistan, the use of solar energy and biomass energy from QTE sources is the main direction of transition to "Green economy".

The interruptions in the energy system that have been observed in recent years are considered as important problems to reduce the energy consumption of all sectors, including industrial enterprises, to implement measures to introduce an effective system of energy saving, to reduce the volume of fuel resources in the production of thermal energy at the level of world standards. In solving these problems, the analysis of international trends in the use of QTE resources in industrial enterprises and the assignment of flexible strategic tasks to them are of urgent importance.

2.Literature review

Although many studies have been conducted by foreign and domestic scientists on the use of alternative energy sources in industrial enterprises, concepts with a unified system for industrial enterprises have not been formed.

QTE is considered as an interrelated factor of achieving the goals of social and economic development. [2] An important feature of a sustainable energy system is its ability to provide the capacity needed without depleting resources. The first approach to creating such a strategy is to increase the effective use of available resources in order to maximize the use of QTE resources. [3] Transitioning from non-renewable sources to QTE should be a key priority in moving towards a sustainable future. Renewable resources are assets that can be used repeatedly to produce electricity, such as wind energy, solar energy, biomass energy, hydropower, etc. [4]

In modern conditions, the stable and independent position of the country is influenced not by the wealth of natural resources or large-scale production, but by the high level of innovative indicators. I.G.Salimyanova, M.G.Treiman [5] researches about the advantages of using QTE sources of industrial enterprises. In this study, it is based on the fact that the use of renewable energy sources in industrial enterprises is the latest innovative approach.

There are also many studies on the effective use of non-traditional energy sources (solar, hydro, geothermal, biomass energy, wind energy) in saving energy resources. QTE is a key component of sustainable development. [6] New energy developments and sources in turn create jobs and export opportunities in growing markets. There are various strategies for promoting emerging energy technologies. A number of factors can influence the choice of strategy, such as available resources, the state of networks, the innovation system, etc. The issue of developing domestic markets to strengthen local industrial enterprises that can ultimately contribute to global exports is also prioritized. [7]

G. N. Ryazanova [8] studied the research on determining the balance of

supply and demand for renewable energy sources in industrial enterprises. In the studies of I.K. Sharapova [9], economic efficiency was calculated based on the use of renewable energy sources in the automobile industry. S.V. on the evaluation of the efficiency of integration of QTE sources into the power supply system of the industrial enterprise. Podkovalnikov, M.A. Studies were conducted by Polomoshina [10].

In the research conducted by E. Taibi, D. Giyelen, M. Bazilians [11], it was predicted that by 2050, 21 percent of the final energy demand and the use of raw materials in the manufacturing industry could be renewable sources. In addition, if the share of renewable sources in energy production is assumed to be 50%, it is based on the fact that in 2050 the share of direct and indirect use of QTE sources will increase to 31%. Another study aimed at predicting the future of QTE in various industries such as industrial, automotive, power generation was conducted by M. K. G. Deshmukh et al.[12]

Energy security is one of the main problems of today's global economy. [13] Several scientists and institutions are promoting the transition to a 100% green concept as a final and sustainable solution to these issues. [14]

There are two main sources of QTE generation: wind power and solar power. The fact that their prices are falling on a global scale is an important factor for the economy of developing countries. The application of these technologies has several benefits, including jobs, economic growth, electrification for urban and rural communities, new skills, poverty reduction, environmental protection and climate change control. It will also help develop the local industry for the production of spare parts for solar and wind power plants. [15]

Most of the research conducted in Uzbekistan on this problem is devoted to technological problems, and the main focus is on the identification of alternative energy sources and research on their technological solutions.

In the research carried out by A. Imamov and others [16], the creation and

implementation of standards for the use and consumption of QTE, the development of the national program of energy saving in economic sectors and social objects, the creation and development of new devices, equipment and spare parts related to non-traditional energy offers for release.

Z.F. Fakhriddinova, Kh.Kh. Rejapov have analyzed the sources of renewable electricity production in Uzbekistan and the level of their use. [17]

In the research conducted by D. Odinayev, the implementation of investment projects for the development of renewable energy and the important directions of the state policy conducted in this regard in the country were analyzed. [18]

Sh.S. Khakimova discussed the scientific research carried out in Uzbekistan on the creation of renewable alternative energy sources. [19]

In general, in Uzbekistan, there are not enough scientific studies devoted to the scientific, methodological and practical issues of creating organizational and economic mechanisms of using QTE resources in industrial enterprises.

3. Analysis and results

Uzbekistan is among the countries that have achieved energy independence, the sources of electricity production in the country are natural gas and oil products. More attention is being paid to saving hydrocarbon resources of renewable energy sources, ensuring energy security of the country, as well as introducing energy-saving technologies in industry. Uzbekistan is a country rich in traditional energy resources: natural gas, coal, oil, shale, uranium and hydropower resources, except for uranium and oil shale, all other energy sources are actively used in the country's energy balance.

The attractiveness of QTE sources is related to the inexhaustibility of these resources, price independence in world energy markets, and environmental cleanliness. In general, taking into account that traditional energy has a negative impact on the environment both at the national and global levels, deep reforms are

being implemented in all countries to create an alternative energy system.

The benefits of using renewable energy sources are numerous and provide far-reaching benefits for people, communities and the planet as a whole. Here are some of the main advantages:

Environmental benefits:

Reduced Greenhouse Gas Emissions: Renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, hydro, and biomass produce little or no greenhouse gas emissions during electricity production, helping to mitigate climate change and reduce air pollution.

Conservation of natural resources: Unlike fossil fuels, renewable energy sources are derived from inexhaustible natural resources such as sunlight, wind, and water, which helps conserve finite resources and reduce environmental degradation associated with resource extraction. .

Energy independence and security:

Diversification of energy sources: Investing in renewable energy diversifies the energy mix and reduces dependence on limited and imported fossil fuels, increases energy security and reduces vulnerability to supply disruptions and price fluctuations in global energy markets.

Localized energy production: Renewable energy technologies can be used on a variety of scales, from small-scale solar panels to large wind farms, enabling decentralized energy production and reducing dependence on centralized energy infrastructure.

Economic benefit:

Job creation and economic growth: The renewable energy sector is a major source of job creation and economic growth, offering employment opportunities in manufacturing, installation, maintenance, research and development. is enough. Investments in renewable energy sources stimulate the local economy and contribute to long-term sustainable development.

Cost competitiveness: The cost of renewable energy technologies such as solar

and wind has fallen significantly in recent years, making them more competitive with fossil fuels in many regions. As renewable energy becomes cheaper, it offers economic advantages over conventional energy sources.

Public health and safety: Reduced air and water pollution: By replacing fossil fuel-based energy production, renewable energy sources help reduce air and water pollution associated with conventional energy production, which improves public health and the environment. - improves the quality of the environment.

Increase disaster resilience: Distributed renewable energy systems such as rooftop solar panels and microgrids increase resilience to natural disasters and grid outages by providing communities with backup power and energy independence during emergencies.

Social and Equality Benefits:

Energy Access: Renewable energy technologies provide opportunities for low-income communities, rural areas, and developing countries to expand access to clean and affordable energy, improve energy equity, and address energy poverty.

Community Participation and Ownership: Community-based renewable energy projects enable local communities to participate in energy decision-making, promote community ownership of energy resources, and create socioeconomic benefits for residents through revenue sharing and community investment.

Overall, the benefits of using renewable energy sources go beyond environmental considerations to include economic, social and health benefits, contributing to a more sustainable and sustainable energy future.

However, these energy sources also have a number of negative effects. This includes the low current density (small amount of energy flowing through a given area per unit time) and the transient voltage variability of most QTE sources. The first case requires large areas of power plants to generate usable energy flow (receptive surfaces of solar devices, area of windmills, extended dams of tidal power plants, etc.). This leads to high material consumption of such devices and, as

a result, an increase in net investment compared to traditional power plants. Research shows that many alternative energy systems pay for themselves due to lower operating costs.

According to the information of the international renewable energy community "REN21" (GLOBAL STATUS REPORT) in 2022, the energy demand for industry and agriculture made up 31% of the total energy consumption, of which 29% is the contribution of industry.

The demand for renewable energy is constantly increasing in the world. However, not all countries have paid enough attention to it. According to "RENEWABLES 2022 GLOBAL STATUS REPORT", one country has joined the list of countries with QTE goals in 2020-2021. There are 164 countries with QTE policies. And there are no countries in the world with 100 percent renewable heating and cooling targets.

Despite the continued expansion of renewable energy around the world, significant challenges remain. They include:

- some QTE markets are experiencing a slowdown in growth based on short-term, unpredictable losses, such as Vietnam's solar panel technology losses in 2021;
- Lengthy permitting processes and other regulatory barriers to renewable energy use remain an obstacle to the development of QTE sources in many countries. The EU's REPowerEU plan for early 2022 included, among other measures, speeding up authorization processes.
- Unstable supply chains (related to the concentration of technology suppliers in a few countries) delaying projects and high costs create high price risks for short investors. This affects the economic feasibility of the projects.
- the limitation of copper, nickel and other resources used in the application of QTE resources necessary to achieve the global climate goals also causes problems in this system.

Globally, the industrial sector is one of the largest energy users, consuming

29% of global total final energy consumption in 2022. Iron and steel is one of the most energy-intensive sub-sectors, accounting for 17% of industrial energy consumption, followed by the chemical industry with a share of 15%.

The share of electricity used in industry and agriculture increased from 24% in 2009 to 29% in 2019. The use of renewable electricity in industry increased by 80% in 2009-2019, the number of renewable sources in industry and agriculture increased by 3.6 percentage points in 2009-2019, and the total final energy consumption in these sectors was 16.1%. Half of the energy provided by renewable sources is used for electricity production, and the rest for heat production, mainly using bioenergy.

A total of 175 gigawatts (GW) of new solar installations were installed worldwide in 2021 — up 36 GW from 2020. This was the largest annual increase in capacity on record. The total global capacity of solar photovoltaic power plants was 942 GW (Fig. 1).

By the end of 2021, at least seven countries in the world will have enough capacity to meet at least 10 percent of their electricity demand through solar energy. Also, 18 countries have installed enough solar electricity capacity to meet 5 percent of their solar energy needs. The highest share of solar electricity was in Australia at 15.5%, Spain at 14.2%, Greece at 13.6%, Honduras at 12.9%, the Netherlands at 11.8%, Chile at 10.9% and Germany at 10.9%. . Overall, solar power generation contributed around 5% of global electricity generation.

Fig.1. Global solar PV capacity and annual additions 2011-2021

The industrial sector has energy needs of different voltages. It covers industries with low temperature process heat requirements (such as food and beverage, mining, pulp and paper) where renewable sources have the highest voltage, as well as industries with high temperature requirements for process heat (such as construction there are problems in industries such as production of products, chemicals, iron and steel smelting). In these industries, QTE has limitations in meeting this type of heat requirements (> 400°C). The main options for decarbonization (creating thermal power without carbonate anhydride) in these sectors are related to electrification, and it would be appropriate if based on energy efficiency, biomass in gasification processes, as well as renewable hydrogen.

The industrial sector is a difficult sector to decarbonise, being heavily dependent on fossil fuels in part due to high temperature requirements and the use of fossil materials for production. Roadmaps and ongoing reforms to prepare

industries for these processes should be seen as necessary actions to reduce CO₂ emissions, including through carbon pricing, energy efficiency and QTE policies.

In 2021, the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO) launched an initiative for deep decarbonization of industry, under which several countries set targets to purchase low-carbon steel and concrete between 25% and 40% of domestic material demand. Since 2016, at least 10 countries (as well as the European Union) have developed specific industrial decontamination roadmaps that include QTE and the use of renewable hydrogen.

In 2021, it announced a strategy to decarbonise the UK industry, focusing on paper, iron and steel, cement and chemicals and other industries. The main goal of this strategy is to make the emissions of industrial enterprises equal to zero, which corresponds to 1/6 of industrial production. Some countries are developing national plans to reduce dependence on fertilizers and encourage domestic production of chemicals through renewable hydrogen.

Another solution to decarbonization is the formation of industrial clusters, which will provide the opportunity to relatively reduce the harmful gases of the industry and the fees for emissions. This experience has been used in China since 2013, and in 2021, 52 low-carbon industrial clusters were established. In China's Suzhou Industrial Park, more than 75% of energy use comes from renewable sources, the highest proportion among China's national development zones. [20] Between 2016 and 2019, park energy consumption increased by 15%, while energy intensity per unit of GDP decreased by approximately 10%. [21]

In early 2022, four global cluster facilities in Australia, Spain and the UK are implementing projects to transition to Net Zero. The Net Zero initiative was launched by the World Economic Forum, Accenture and the Electric Power Research Institute. This cluster approach focuses on savings and cost reduction through heat integration and utility-scale renewables and enabling technologies, including solar thermal, solar panels, QTE.

- In addition to the above, there are still important problems to increase the utilization of QTE resources in the industrial sector. These include:
- - the costs of reducing CO2 emissions in high-temperature processes of heavy industry remain high, especially since many sectors of heavy industry still use coal, gas and oil-based energies;
- - as in other sectors, fossil fuel subsidies are limiting investment in energy efficiency and QTE to decarbonize the industrial sector. Materials and products in the industrial sector are sold at a low margin in a competitive market, which further limits opportunities;
- - the demand for energy in some sub-sectors of steel and chemical industry has a high growth tendency in developing countries. These sectors have not yet innovated enough to limit CO2 emissions;
- - the transition to renewable energy may increase the number of closed assets across the industrial sector. It is estimated that replacing coal-fired blast furnaces with electricity in the steel industry alone would require \$70 billion in additional assets. This situation leads to the limitation of motives for the transition of the industry to renewable energy sources;
- - in general, the crisis of energy obtained from fossil resources has become a global problem that threatens all countries. In response to this problem, countries have planned medium-term strategies to reduce dependence on fossil fuels and increase national and regional energy security.

4.Conclusions and recommendations

Under such conditions, clear road maps should be developed for the implementation of reforms aimed at solving this issue in Uzbekistan. Based on the study of international experiences, it is suggested to use the following experiences in order to achieve energy efficiency and increase the renewable energy capacity of industrial enterprises in Uzbekistan:

- in the countries of the world, the industrial sector continues to pay less attention to this policy than other end-use sectors of energy. Accordingly, it is necessary to develop a QTE policy for industry in Uzbekistan. It is proposed to use the experiences of China and Germany;

- several countries on the use of renewable hydrogen sources in 2021, 38 countries, Africa, Latin America and the European Union have their own strategies. An analysis of existing roadmaps shows that most of them focus on the expansion of hydrogen production based on renewable sources. Saudi Arabia has announced plans to build hydrogen electrolysis plants, relying entirely on renewable electricity. Among such countries, Uzbekistan has also developed a strategy to increase the production of renewable hydrogen. Continuing this trend, its further expansion should be defined as the main strategic direction;

- modern bioenergy provided 5.6% of final global energy demand in 2020, which accounted for 47% of all QTE in final energy consumption. The development of the bioenergy sector is a targeted strategic direction for Uzbekistan. The reason is that by 2021, the level of recycling of industrial and solid household waste in Uzbekistan is less than 30%;

Financial incentives for the use of renewable energy sources in the industrial sector have been considered the most widespread policy in the world. During 2021, several European countries implemented such policies: Austria launched a grant program for large industrial solar thermal plants, and Spain implemented a grant program for renewable heat sources in industrial processes. In Spain, the industry and service sectors have allocated €108 million (US\$122 million) in grants to support the financing of 51 solar energy projects with a total capacity of 62 MW. Based on this, it is appropriate to announce grant programs aimed at the implementation of large-scale projects on the use of QTE resources in industrial sectors in Uzbekistan;

China's centralized power market will grow by about 15% in 2021, while

distributed solar will grow by 37%. The fact that 2021 is the last year of using central government subsidies for residential systems gave high motivation to business entities. China's total electricity generation (from all sources) increased by 9.8 percent, and solar electricity generation increased by 25.2 percent to 327 terawatt-hours (TWh). The share of solar power plants in total production increased from 3.4 percent in 2020 to 15 percent. to 3.9% in 2021.²⁰ China's solar decline averaged 2% in 2021, unchanged from the previous two years. Accordingly, it is appropriate to further expand the practice of using specific incentive mechanisms and subsidies for industrial enterprises in the use of solar energy in Uzbekistan.

Taking into account that more than 1,400 institutional investors and institutions with a total value of more than 39 trillion US dollars in 2021 have committed to partially or completely abandon fossil fuels in the world, there is a tendency to attract investments in investment projects in the field of QTE. Based on this trend, it is necessary to create specific mechanisms for expanding investments and attracting foreign investors in the directions of providing industry with QTE in Uzbekistan.

The analysis and results show that advances in wind and solar power, energy storage technologies, sector integration, and demand-side flexibility are laying the foundations for complete QTE systems. Building a renewable energy system, innovations in energy storage technologies allow industrial enterprises to minimize costs, increase reliability and help balance the fluctuations of variable renewable sources. Accordingly, the expansion of the use of QTE in the industry and the implementation of innovations in this regard should be set as priority strategic goals.

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